

PROBLEMS OF GENERATION Z YOUTH IN HIGHER EDUCATION: CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS

Valehov S.

National Defense University

Heydar Aliyev Military Institute

Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-0357-2641>

ABSTRACT

The article comprehensively analyzes the problems faced by Generation Z students during their higher education. Factors such as digitization, information overload, frequent distraction, motivation problems, changing demands in the labor market, and the ineffectiveness of existing traditional education methods are examined.

At the same time, directions for solving these problems through the application of modern pedagogical approaches, personalized education models, and technologies are presented. When preparing the article, academic sources were cited and the necessity of improving modern higher education to meet the requirements was substantiated.

Keywords: generation z, higher education, motivation, educational problems, personalized education.

Introduction

Generation Z refers to those born approximately between 1997 and 2012. They are a generation that was formed during the rapid development of technology, grew up in a digital environment, and has radically different information acquisition habits (Prensky, 2001). This generation is characterized as “digital natives” and their learning behaviors are significantly different from previous generations (Tapscott, 2009).

Modern higher education systems, on the other hand, are usually built on the principles of the industrial era. This mismatch creates serious problems for Generation Z students and necessitates structural changes in the education system (Selwyn, 2016).

Characteristics of Generation Z youth

The main characteristics of Generation Z students (cadets, trainees) are as follows:

- Quick adaptation to digital technologies
- Fast perception of information
- Multitasking tendency
- Short attention span
- Need for an individualized approach

Studies show that Generation Z students are not interested in traditional lecture methods and prefer interactive, technology-based learning methods (Oblinger & Oblinger, 2005).

Main problems

1) Ineffectiveness of traditional educational methods

The lecture-based learning model widely used in higher education is not effective enough for Generation Z. This model encourages passive learning and limits active participation of students (Freeman et al., 2014; S.A.Valehov et al., 2016).

2) Attention and motivation problems

Young people growing up in a digital environment have difficulty with activities that require long-term attention. Social media and other digital platforms increase attentional bias (Rosen et al., 2013).

3) Information overload and superficial knowledge

Although widespread access to the Internet provides students with a large amount of information, this leads to a decrease in deep learning in them (Carr, 2010). Students often settle for superficial information.

4) Mismatch between the labor market and educational programs

Higher education programs often do not meet the real demands of the labor market. This ultimately leads to graduates having difficulty finding a job (World Economic Forum, 2020).

5) Psychological and social problems

The number of cases of stress, anxiety and depression among Generation Z continues to increase. Academic pressure and an uncertain future caused by teaching deepen these problems (Twenge, 2017).

6) Improper teacher-student relationship

Generation Z does not accept an authoritarian attitude. Therefore, open questions and discussions should be encouraged, an environment should be created that accepts that it is normal to make mistakes, and students' opinions should be valued. Knowing that they are dependent on technology, digital tools (for example, short videos and visual materials) should be used in a professional context. The teacher should fulfill the role of both a knowledge transfer and a mentor who provides direction in a balanced way.

Causes of problems

The main causes of problems in higher education of Generation Z youth are:

- Outdated structure of the education system
- Uncontrolled use of technology
- Lack of an individualized approach
- Difficulties in adapting teachers to new methods
- Lack of practical experience

These factors reduce the effectiveness of the educational process and negatively affect student motivation.

Solution directions (our conclusions)

1) Integration of digital technologies with education (S.A.Valehov et al., 2025).

The application of artificial intelligence, online platforms and interactive tools in the educational process increases student interest (Luckin, 2016).

2) Personalized education models

The basis of individualization is getting to know the student. Using surveys, tests, and digital tracking tools, the student

- Learning speed and level are determined
- Interests and motivational factors are analyzed

- Learning style (visual, auditory, or practical) is determined

The difficulty level of the material is changed according to the student's responses. Developing educational programs that are tailored to the individual characteristics of each student increases effectiveness (artificial intelligence-based educational systems).

3) Active learning methods

- Problem-based learning
- Project-based learning
- Case study approach

These methods develop students' analytical and critical thinking skills (S.A.Valehov et al., 2016).

4) Integration of education with the labor market

Universities should cooperate more closely with the business world and increase opportunities for practical experience.

5) Psychological support systems

Psychological support systems help students:

- Deal with stress and tension
- Maintain motivation
- Social adaptation
- Solve personal and academic problems. The organization of psychological services for students has a positive impact on their educational success and reduces the risk of dropping out.

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Conclusion

The transformation of higher education for Generation Z is inevitable. Traditional methods are no longer effective and innovative approaches are required. It is important for the education system to be flexible, technology-oriented and student-centered.

The conducted analyses show that the higher education problems of Generation Z youth are complex and require a systematic approach. Digitalization, personalized education and integration with the labor market are the main priority areas. If modern higher education systems do not adapt to these changes, their effectiveness will seriously decrease.

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